

THE EMERGENCE OF THE METHODS OF THE RUSSIAN LANGUAGE AS A SCIENCE

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Abstract. *This article examines the emergence of the methodology of the Russian language as a science, examines its historical roots and stages of formation. The methodology of teaching the Russian language, as an independent scientific discipline, has gone a long way of development, starting from its inception in the XIX century and up to the present day. In the first part of the work, attention is paid to the historical prerequisites for the formation of the methodology of teaching the Russian language. The second section is devoted to the key stages of the formation of the methodology. The methods and approaches that were used in various periods, as well as their evolution under the influence of social, cultural and political factors, are considered in detail. In this context, the work of such scientists as Konstantin Ushinsky, TALadyzhenskaya and others, whose works have become fundamental in the formation of teaching methods, is studied.*

Keywords: *methodology, history, ability, development of creative abilities, methods, literary reading lesson, relevance, techniques, activation.*

ВОЗНИКНОВЕНИЕ МЕТОДА РУССКОГО ЯЗЫКА КАК НАУКИ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматривается становление методологии русского языка как науки, рассматриваются ее исторические корни и этапы становления. Методика преподавания русского языка, как самостоятельная научная дисциплина, прошла большой путь развития, начиная с момента ее зарождения в XIX веке и до наших дней. Исторические предпосылки формирования методики преподавания русского языка. Второй раздел посвящен ключевым этапам формирования методики. Подробно рассмотрены методы и подходы, которые использовались в различные периоды, а также их эволюция под влиянием социальных, культурных и политических факторов. В этом контексте изучаются работы таких ученых, как Константин Ушинский, Т.А. Ладыженская и других, труды которых стали основополагающими в формировании методики обучения.*

Ключевые слова: *методика, история, способности, развитие творческих способностей, методы, урок литературного чтения, актуальность, приемы, активизация.*

The emergence of the methodology of the Russian language as a science is associated with the appearance in 1844 of the book “On Teaching the Russian Language” by the outstanding linguist, historian, teacher F.I. Buslaev » Fedor Ivanovich Buslaev – humanist; for him, a person is a bearer of beautiful, high impulses of the soul.

The scientist believes that To teach the language means to develop the spiritual abilities of students, and this is impossible without “methods”. He differentiates "educational method" and "scientific method", i.e. methods of teaching and research. Objectives of the educational methodology: rely on teaching experience, analysis of learning results; study the student’s personality; ensure the scientific reliability of the material; to instill in the student “a desire for serious studies and awaken a love for science”

K.D. Ushinsky made a great contribution to the development of methods of teaching the Russian language to junior schoolchildren. His works are addressed to the public primary school.

Ushinsky created such textbooks as “Children’s World” and “Native Word”. The scientist’s methodological ideas are still relevant today.

According to K.D. Ushinsky, language acquisition is a multifaceted activity, but its core should be a grammar course that has a practical focus. This course reveals the logic of language, introduces the norms of declinations, conjugations, word combinations, develops the student’s thinking and gift of words. Schoolchildren must understand the role of linguistic forms in conveying meaning and general meaning, therefore the study of grammar must begin from the text, from the sentence.

K.D. Ushinsky builds all grammatical topics on the discovery of the studied forms in A. Pushkin’s “The Tale of the Fisherman and the Fish” and the identification of their functions. This is how the meanings of case forms of nouns, imperative mood of verbs, etc. are learned. According to the scientist, students’ speech should develop on the best examples of literature of a language, its correctness is ensured by grammar. K.D. Ushinsky also proposed a system of presentations and compositions, highly appreciating the independent speech of children, writing: “Compositions, if by them we mean exercises of the gift of speech, should be the main thing classes in the lessons of the native language, but they must really be exercises, i.e. . if possible, through the independent efforts of students, to express orally or in writing an independent thought, and not by stitching together other people’s phrases” (Collected works: in 11 vols. T. 5. M., 1949. P. 333). Language exercises should be varied and interconnected. The scientist valued spelling abilities and skills very highly: they should be firmly established at the earliest stages of learning. In spelling, he recognized the role of rules, but highly valued the role of the general linguistic culture.

In the method of teaching reading, K.D. Ushinsky developed the fundamentals of the method of explanatory reading, while carefully selecting classical texts, but was not carried away by the question accepted at that time but a reactive method of analyzing the content and language of what was read. However, he introduced into the textbook “Native Word” a system of logical-stylistic exercises, among which he especially appreciated the operation of comparison, and built conversations and stories on its basis.

K.D. Ushinsky also introduced a new method of teaching literacy - on a sound basis, with a combination of analytical and synthetic work of students. The scientist called his method historical, since he reproduced the discovery of sound writing by our distant ancestors: sounds were highlighted in the word, they were designated by letters. His ability to read was secondary, it followed writing. This logic was rejected by its successors.

At the present stage, this method is taken as a basis, receiving the name of the sound analytical-synthetic method, with modifications it is still used today.

The merits of L.N. Tolstoy in the development of literacy teaching methods

The great Russian writer Lev Nikolaevich Tolstoy also left a big mark on the methodology of the Russian (native) language. Leo Tolstoy showed himself as a philosopher, thinker and teacher in his pedagogical activities. He created his own method of teaching literacy - auditory and compiled the “ABC” in 4 books (1873), which he repeatedly called the main task of his life (13 years of work!).

For “ABC” the writer wrote more than 600 stories and many of this heritage are now being republished and form a reading fund for younger schoolchildren, their moral content has a beneficial effect on several generations of young people. Leo Tolstoy himself worked as a teacher at the Yasnaya Polyanskaya elementary school, and he himself introduced the method of free education. He created a creative direction in the development of students' speech. He wrote about the awakening of the spiritual strength of schoolchildren, their creative takeoff in the article “Who should learn to write from whom: the peasant children from us or from the peasant children?” L.N. Tolstoy wrote: “I cannot enter the school... so as not to experience direct physical anxiety, as if to look through Lomonosov, Pushkin, Glinka, Ostrogradsky and somehow find out who needs what” (ABC. New ABC. M. 1978. P. 8). Modern “pedagogy of non-violence” and creative methods are rooted in the rich storehouse of ideas, plans, and undertakings of this extraordinary person.

The end of the 19th and the beginning of the 20th century. – this is a time of extraordinary rise of creative thought in pedagogy and methods of the Russian language.

New curricula and textbooks are being created for different types of schools and for different teaching concepts.

Scientists and methodologists left a deep imprint on the methodology of that time:

* I.I. Sreznevsky - justified the goals and content of the academic subject “Russian language” in the national primary school;

* D.I. Tikhomirov is the author and publisher of a number of Russian language textbooks. He has developed a teaching aid for teachers “What and how to teach in Russian language lessons”;

* I.I. Paulson is the author of many textbooks, compiler of books for reading;

* I.A. Korf - he developed a new version of the methodology for teaching literacy;

* N.V. Bunakov – teacher of teachers, methodologist and teacher, developer of methods for developing students’ speech;

* A.Ya. Ostrogorsky – author-compiler of the best literary anthologies “The Living Word”;

* A.D. Alferov – method theorist, author of fundamental work on the method;

* Ts.P. Baltalon - led a new direction in the literary education of schoolchildren, developed a method for students’ independent choice of books and extracurricular reading;

* V.P. Vakhterov is the creator of a new pedagogy, the author of one of the best anthologies “The World in Stories for Children” and many others.

Until the middle of the 20th century. such outstanding linguists as V.I. Chernyshov (substantiated the theory of expressive reading), L.V. Shcherba (studied the methodology of the methodology, supervised the creation Animation of Russian language textbooks), A.V. Mirtov (development and culture of speech), M.V. Ushakov (spelling method), M.A. Rybnikova (literary reading method), K.B. Barkhin (creative activity of schoolchildren in the field of speech), E.S. Solovyova (drama ation, speech, reading, anthology “Native Speech”), P.O. Afanasyev (general theoretical foundations of Russian language methods).

Mastery of speech, oral and written, is recognized as the main pragmatic task of the native language course. Strengthening the position of speech in the philological education of schoolchildren was one of the reasons for the revival of rhetoric in accessible elements, often under the name of “children’s rhetoric” (T.A. Ladyzhens) which and its scientific school). Rhetoric connects the theoretical study of language, the general cultural development of students with the needs of communication, persuasion with words, monologue and dialogue. This is a search for optimal communication algorithms in modern conditions.

A new direction has also become the study of the speech of preschool and school-age children. The largest researcher in this area was A.N. Gvozdev (1892–1959). He described the

process of children mastering the pronunciation side of speech, vocabulary and especially the grammatical structure of speech, established periodization in speech development, created the basis for educational practices. The scientist's followers were: M.P. Feofanov, who studied syntactic connections in the speech of junior schoolchildren in the 50s, S.N. Tseitlin, who studied speech errors. In the 70s, the speech of a six-year-old child was studied by the "Speech" group under the leadership of T.A. Ladyzhenskaya.

The methodology of spelling is devoted to the research of N.S. Rozhdestvensky (1892–1981). His views are reflected in the monograph "Properties of Russian spelling as the basis of its teaching methods." For many years he, as the author of the textbook "Russian Language," determined the traditional direction in theoretical and practical methods.

In the field of reading methods and literature, after several decades of underestimation of classical works, there is an increasing tendency to increase interest in the classics, especially in the works of E.C. Vievoy (1869–1945), author-compiler of "Native Speech" in 4 books, M.S. Vasilyeva, M. I. Omorokova and others.

At the end of the 80s, the anthology "Native Speech" was created by M.V. Golovanov, V.G. Goretsky and L.F. Klimanova. This book implements the principles and methodological guidelines of literary reading: the development of literature in Russia is shown, the work of the largest poets and writers is presented in a selection their works, literary concepts, etc., were introduced, as well as the works of some forgotten writers.

In the methodology of teaching literacy, by the 60s there was a critical explosion directed against the official method - the sound analytical-synthetic method performed by S.P. Redozub va (the so-called primer of the APN of the RSFSR). Criticism came from D.B. Elkonin, who created his own primer and method of teaching reading by the end of the 60s; I.I. Grushnikov, A.V. Yankovskaya, A. Lemeni-Makedon and others. Criticism accelerated the search: by the end of the decade, A.F. Shanko came out with a justification for the soundological method of teacher Ilyukevich. In 1969, the first, experimental version of the "Primer" by V.G. Goretsky, V.A. Kiryushkin and A.F. Shanko appeared, which is used in school to this day (also in the "ABC" version). By the beginning of the 90s, primers by V.A. Levin and V.V. Repkin, N.V. Nechaeva, "Moscow Primer", "Zemsky Primer", "Quick Primer" by V.G. Goretsky and co-authors appeared. All primers are very different from one another and are based on their own concepts.

It should be added that in the 20th century. The method of initial teaching of Russian as a non-native language for the so-called national schools received very intensive development (N.M. Shansky, E. Bystrova, E.I. Kotok, N.B. Ekba and many others).

The famous Russian linguist and methodologist L.V. Shcherba was looking for answers to the following questions: is methodology a science or an art? What guides you when choosing a teaching method? How does language acquisition occur in conditions of bilingualism? How to develop listening comprehension of your native speech? He was the first to understand the need to use speech theory in school methods: distinguishing speech activity in language (speaking, listening, writing, reading), linguistic material (total the essence of everything spoken and written) and the system of language, he made an attempt to put this distinction into the basis of teaching methods. He paid a lot of attention to spelling methods - the most pressing issue in school in the 20s, which has not lost its urgency today.

Historically, a closely knit cycle of philological subjects or “Russian Literature” has developed in the Russian elementary school. He united all language subjects and skills - from elementary literacy to literature and rhetoric, and sometimes included foreign languages, theater, music, fine arts and served a central center of universal culture.

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